

Design and Communication Phenomenon in the Metaverse

Hsu Hung-Pin *

** Graduate Institute of Architecture, National Chiao Tung University
Hsinchu City, Taiwan, ncs@arch.nctu.edu.tw*

Abstract: The digital media influence almost every facet of life. In recent years, the related study of the digital design focuses on the cognitive behavior as well as media. However, there are few discussions on the influences of digital design environment between design communication behavior of designers. With the network communicative function consolidated into digital environment, the birth of the Metaverse should be widely discussed on design communication behavior. This research adopts usability testing to study the conversion of original habit of the design as well as communication behavior of the designer, the conversion that designer is from the conventional digital environment into the Metaverse. Finally, a preliminary prototype of friendly digital environment is presented.

Key words: *Metaverse, Design Communication, Usability.*

1. Introduction

With the popularity of the application of digital technology, the new type of the architectures as well as architects is growing to develop. The landscape which is build based on the digital virtual scene among the media, game or network space are to go in for large-scale construction. The architects engaged in virtual space greet the totally novel working characteristic and design object with the peculiar appearance. The new generation of the discipline of the designers is rising quietly. [7]

As the design procedure is experiencing the birth of the digital media and to change in recent years, the globalized spread effect of the communication technology also impact the field of digital media design. The integrated digital environment provides some functions of producing, consuming and communication in single interface, and moreover, in the virtual network space, establishes the scale villages of economical, societal and cultural. The innovation that designers faced in the virtual landscape takes place on the non-traditional new digital media, an enterprise environment that prompts the designers much close to the proprietors and design object in virtual space. The update of the landscape is accompanied with the update of society. [1, 5, 6]

In a series of papers in architecture, as to the virtual environment, they discuss collaborative design for the principal. However, in the development of user requirement-oriented software, we should pay more attention to the research of virtual environment that is focuses on the architecture-oriented purpose. In the new and developing virtual environment, the internet platform, Second Life, is quite classic representation that is not only

the enterprise but also the consuming environment of the virtual architecture, so as to provide designers and proprietors with pipeline for communication and business. Because the procedure of the usability study is a circle of design-test-redesign [8], this study tries to estimate the new environmental interface in two levels: Usability testing and Prototype design.

By using usability testing to proceeding with estimate testing for the device, system or interface, it can reflect the conditions of the targeted users. Among the most of the usability research, it usually organizes the users' behaviors by affinity diagram to present the scope of problems and the key requirement. In addition, by sequence model, we can find out the targeted tasks, and the order as well as strategy of the tasks which the users have finished, so as to clearly figure out the need for testing object to support and modify. [2]

The prototype design is a user-central procedure which can let designer immediately and directly gain the users' feedback. The user environment design model is set up to present the constructive issue of the testing object, and therefore, to reflect the users' feeling on the prototype, so that they can understand how their opinions reflect on the new design object. In this way, the designer can estimate if the new performance is worth developing, and if the users can adopt this new design. The prototype makes the users involved in the design procedure, and totally regards the users as the central concept. [2]

2. Research objective

As discussed above, with the development of network communication technology, a digital environment of single interface with network communication function come into being Metaverse. The essential issue of this research is that what the problems are, the designer is facing, with respect to the design as well as communication behavior of the designer when the circumstance covers from conventional environment into Metaverse. What measures need we adopt to attract the designer to stay in the novel Metaverse? So that the objective of this paper is therefore to find out the design and communication phenomenon in the Metaverse, as well as the gaps between two kinds of digital environments. And finally, we developed a friendly design communicative environment so as to let the designer easily convert the habit to a new environment.

3. Research methodology and process

3.1. Experiment one: Conventional Digital Environment

This experiment focuses on the behavior of the designer engaging in the design communication in the conventional environment, and the experiment is including three stages in the virtual architecture design: the communication of design request, the design of virtual architecture, and the discussion of design results. The purpose of this experiment is to find out how the designers work in the conventional environment while they are on the design communication stage. The following is the definition of the research variables in this experiment.

Experimental environment: In order to simulate the process of design communication between designers and proprietor in the different space, we provided two independent and separated rooms with the same devices. Moreover, each room has one camera and one computer, the former that recorded the behavior of the subjects in the real space while the latter which fit for the design communication request so that we can record in detail the

process of the communication between the subjects. In addition, both computers in the different rooms had set up the software, MORAE, to record the route when using the computer interface.

Subject A: A designer who had had perfect ability of generating concepts utilized the CAD Media, and had been educated with more than three years of digital design. In order to compare with these two experiments, we demanded the subject A had been the user of the internet platform, Second Life, in this experiment.

Subject B: A proprietor, who had never used the CAD Media and never been educated with digital design, would not consider with the request in the process of the digital design, so as to ensure the experiment reliability.

Tools: CAD Media, 3DMax, an instant message software, MSN Message, e-mail, and cell phone. In order to understand the design behavior of the designers, we merely demanded the software for accomplishing the design and devices and interface for communicating. Therefore, the designers could use the internet to search information or other familiar media for the design generation.

Design topic: The single floor architecture which had only two simple elements, for example, doors and windows. In order to control the experimental time, the design topic of this research made the designers to design well and regarded the provided rooms as the major consideration so that the proprietors could ask for the design request.

Time: There were thirty minutes for the two subjects in the different separated rooms to communicate with each other about the design request. Furthermore, the designers continued to design for thirty minutes. During this period, they could still use the provided devices or interface to discuss with the proprietors. In the end of the design, these two subjects have thirty minutes to discuss the design performances. It totaled to spend ninety minutes.

3.2. Experiment two: Metaverse

This experiment is with respect to the behavior of the designer engaging in design communication in the Metaverse. During the process, it also consists of three stages: the communication of design request, the design of virtual architecture, and the discussion of design results. The purpose of this experiment is to find out how the designers work in the Metaverse while they are on the design communication stage. The following is the definition of the research variables in the experiment two.

Subject A: The designer, who was the same as the one in the experiment one, utilized the internet platform, Second Life, to proceed with the design communication. This research demanded the subject A for the professional ability of the design on Second Life that he had used to design on, while demanded the subject A for the manipulating ability of the communication that he must have worked on Second Life for more than one month.

Subject B: The proprietor, who was the same as the one in the experiment one, used Second Life to communicate with the designer. This research demanded the subject B for the manipulating ability of the communication that he must have worked on Second Life for more than one month.

Tools: The design communicative environment of the Metaverse, Second Life. This research merely provided the subjects with Second Life, while the other supply was restricted.

Experiment environment, Design topic, Time: The same as experiment one.

3.3. Analysis

The major analytical data of this research is the visual data recorded from experiment one and two. This research adopts the analytical visual data but not the general methodology, think aloud, so as to make the subjects easily to focus on the experiment and communicate in the process.

In addition, this research takes the verbal data to complement the disadvantage of the visual data, the verbal data that is collected from the specific questions asked by the author after the experiments. We can use the verbal data to figure out the reaction of the subjects and the options they are concerned about [8, 9, 10]. This research consolidates the gathered data based on the previous research methodology and continues to analyze with the following methods of evaluation. [2]

Affinity diagram: By analyzing the data collected from the experiment one and two, we note them in colors, blue, yellow, and red, from bottom to top. And then, we can build the tree affinity diagram by generalizing and arranging these data. The bottom level of blue is the behavior or reaction of the subjects we observed, while the intermediate level of yellow is subjects' behavioral motives generalized from the blue. The top level of red is the principal purposes of the subjects generalized from the yellow. The affinity diagrams are shown in Figure 1 and 2.

According to the Figure 1, the affinity diagram of the conventional environment is mainly divided into four items: Communication, Data Searching, Data Exchanging and Design. The first item includes cell phone and MSN message. The second uses the internet to search the media. The third exchanges the data by MSN message. The fourth uses the software data base and the media from the internet to proceed with the design.

Figure.1 Affinity diagram of the conventional digital environment.

Based on the illustration of Figure 2, the affinity diagram of the Metaverse is mainly separated into three items: Communication, Data Searching and Design. The first item uses the communication function of the texts and the voice provided from Second Life. The second uses the map function provided from Second Life. The searching here does not use keywords to look for the unknown data, but uses the well known information to find the familiar data. The third uses the media provided from Second Life to proceed with the design.

Figure.2 Affinity diagram of the integrated digital environment of internet.

Sequence model: After analyzing the data assembled from the experiment one and two, we can build the sequence model based on the order of the subjects who have finished the tasks. It is shown in the Figure 3 and 4.

According to the Figure 3, the sequence model of the conventional environment is mainly divided into three stages: Communication, Design, and Communication. Three tools are used in this model that subjects search for the design information by internet and use MSN as well as telephone to proceed with the communication of the texts and speaking as well as the data receiving. During the interview, we find that it is evidential for designers and proprietors to have a dialogue by texts in the first stage. However, for discussing conveniently, we change the manner of communication from texts into voice during and after the design. On the other hand, a demarcation line between the second and the third stage is blurry. Even if the not finished task, the architect still continues to discuss with the proprietor by using the supply of the digital environment.

Figure.3 Sequence model of the conventional digital environment.

Based on the illustration of Figure 4, the sequence mode of the Metaverse is mainly separated into two stages: Communication and Design. The subjects choose the location on the building base, and use the text function provided from Second Life to communicate. Sequentially, the designer stats to design according to the design request. After the design, the architecture is presented at the location selected by both architect and proprietor,

and meanwhile, they will inspect the performance. If there are some needs to be modified, repeating the previous steps. However, during the interview, we find that there is only one of three groups to use the searching function because it is difficult to find the right location on Second Life.

Figure.4 Sequence model of the Metaverse.

3.4 Advice on the design of the Metaverse

User Environment Design Model: This study of the design of user environment design model is based on the results of section 3.3, the study that focuses on the circumstance of the Metaverse. Moreover, compared with the conventional environment, this study consolidates the difference into the user environment design model, as shown in Figure 5. The major focus area in this model includes four functions: Voice, Conversation, Transmission, and Browsing, four coming from tools: MSN, cell phone, and internet searching. Illustrating the interaction between functions with arrows, the operation indicates the connection of the functions when one arrow of the focus area points to the other.

Figure.5 User environment design model of the Metaverse.

Prototype: In order to test the function at the suggestion of the user environment design model, mentioned above, the study produces the prototype with the website designing software, Dreamweaver and the vector drawing software, CorelDraw. The prototype of the design of the functions, including Communication function and the Table function as below:

A. Communication function:

The main meaning of the communication function in the prototypes is to create a clear interface to let users could communicate with others. The original communicative environment in the Metaverse just allow users to be able to hear the voice, but not manifest whom they communicate with. This kind of interface design makes both subjects in this research confused when the third or more communicators join the conversation without their agreement. To improve this problem, the interface of communication function in the prototypes use the yellow ring to circle the communicators. And each communicator in this ring would have a personal communicative interface which would change to the yellow color when they speak to others no matter in the text or voice type. Moreover, users could deliver data, control the volume, choose the person they want to talk in the friends list, and connect to the Table function. The example of the prototype of communication function interface design is shown in the figure 6:

Figure.6 The example of prototype of communication function interface.

B. Table function:

There are four sub-functions in the Table function design, including text, picture, map, and information. Those four functions are based on the general habits of use in the conventional digital environment. Those functions design could allow the users to communicate with each others by showing the text, pictures, maps, and information on the table. The Table function improves the visible problem with respect to the avatars in the virtual world and users selves in the real world. Moreover, the user could get the information from other tables used by the Group function at the same time, or from the news in the Metaverse provided from other users by the News function. The Table function is similar to a conversation room or a wall that the users can communicate with each others by sharing different information. The example of the prototype of Table function interface design is shown in the figure 7:

Figure.7 The prototype of table function interface design.

According to the discovery described above, a preliminary prototype of friendly digital environment is presented, as shown in Figure 8. The structure shows five main kinds of functions, including communication, location, design, file, and media. First of all, users could communicate with each other with the text, voice, image, video, face to face functions in the communication category. Among them, the text and voice functions are derived from the communication function in the prototypes, and the image and video functions are derived from the table function in the prototypes. Moreover, the face to face function is to show emotion through the facial expression design. And this part is comparative weak in the Metaverse.

Figure.8 User interface structure of the Metaverse.

The location category allow users through the Map in the Metaverse to point out the location they mean. This function have creat in the Metaverse already and been used most generally. The file category we suggest could allow users to transmit the file in real-time or by virtual mail. The real-time function has already been included in the Metaverse. But based on the need which users would keep their private or send the files as other user outline, and keep the continued and immersion experience. This paper suggest to create a virtual-mail function to allow users send emails in the Metaverse.

The design category allow users to design the products in the Metaverse in the 2D drawing or 3D scale. In the recent interface of the Metaverse, users could only build virtual 3D scale, but not allow to draw down what they thought when they talking about the design issue. Cause drawing is the most important habit in the begin stage of design communication work [3, 4, 11, 12]. So that this paper suggest to create a 2D drawing function to allow the users drawing their thought when they are talking about their design. And the Media category allow users get the data from the database, internet, real world. This category is the same with the current design communicative environment in the Metaverse.

4. Conclusion and discussion

This paper has already presented the preliminary prototype of friendly digital environment as well as user interface structure of the Metaverse. From the result of the analysis of visual and verbal data of experiments, the author derives the phenomena of communication as well as the design of designer in the Metaverse.

When the designer communicates with the proprietor in the Metaverse, the behavior of communication is restricted. First of all, the designer in the conventional digital environment communicates by voice, image and text from cell phone, MSN message, and internet searching. There is no difference in the behavior of general people familiar with the digital technology. However, communicating by texts or voice arriving to the assigned location, the people in the Metaverse lack for the instantaneous reaction in despite of experiencing the scene ambiance in virtual space.

On the other hand, it is so mature of the conventional digital environment that the designer can search for the relevant resources to aid design on the internet when designing the virtual architecture. Nevertheless, the possibility of the design development is limited by the lack of the aid interface that the designer in the Metaverse can merely utilizes the tools supported by the system.

5. References

- [1] Abdellatif, R. and C. Calderon. (2007). SecondLife: A Computer-Mediated Tool for Distance-Learning in Architecture Education? *Proceedings of the ASCAAD 2007 Conference*, (pp. 17-34). Alexandria, Egypt.
- [2] Beyer, H. and Holtzblatt, K. (1997). *Contextual design: defining customer-centered systems*. San Francisco, CA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.
- [3] Goldschmidt, G. (1994). On visual design thinking: the via kids of architecture, *Design Studies*, 15(2), 158-174.
- [4] Dorst, K. and J. Dijkhuis (1995). Comparing paradigms for describing design activity, *Design Studies*, 16(2): 261-274.
- [5] Liu, Y. T., (2001). Spatial representation of design thinking in cyberspace. *Proceedings of the Visual and Spatial Reasoning in Design II*, (pp. 25-40). Australia: University of Sydney.
- [6] Lynch, K., (1975). *Ground for Utopia*. In *Responding to Social Change*, B. Honikman ed., EDRA 6, Stroudsburg, Pa.: Dawen, Hutchinson and Ross
- [7] Norman, D. A. (2000). *The psychology of everyday things*. New York: Basic Books
- [8] Preece, J. (1998). *A guide to usability: human factors in computing*. Wokingham, England: Addison-Wesley.
- [9] Rosenman, M. A., Smith, G., Maher, M. L., Ding, L., Marchant, D., (2007). Multidisciplinary collaborative design in virtual environments. *Automation in Construction*, 16, 37-44.
- [10] Shneiderman, B. (1997). *Designing the user interface*. Reading, Mass: Addison Wesley Longman.

[11] Suwa, M. and Tversky, B. (1997). What do architects and students perceive in their design sketches? A protocol analysis, *Design Studies*, 18(4): 385-403.

[12] Suwa, M., Purcell, T. and Gero, J. (1998). Macroscopic analysis of design processes based on a scheme for coding designer's cognitive actions, *Design Studies*, 19(4): 455-483.